

On how VoIP attacks foster the malicious call ecosystem

J. Carrillo-Mondéjar, J.L. Martinez and G. Suarez-Tangil

Abstract—Switched telephone networks have existed for a long time, and through technological development, cellular networks and Voice over IP (VoIP) have been incorporated into this ecosystem, integrating more modern ways of communication into the telephone system. The evolution of this technology has also led to an increase in the number and sophistication of the techniques used by criminals to perpetrate fraud. Specifically, with the emergence of VoIP, attackers can now adapt tools commonly used by cybercriminals, such as botnets, to make their attacks more complex and insidious. For example, through bots they can dial multiple numbers automatically, enabling them to target a greater number of victims, and do so more quickly. While recent studies have shed light on how certain parts of this ecosystem work, it is still unclear how attacks on VoIP systems contribute to this type of fraud. In this paper, we build a VoIP honeypot and study how fraudsters first compromise and then use our system. We present an overview of how attackers obtain access to our honeypot and the actions they perform through live measurement. Unlike previous works, we focus on how criminals leverage a compromised (i.e., free) VoIP infrastructure to develop commodity telephony fraud. We provide unique insights into the origin of the attacks and the destination of calls made through our architecture. Finally, we analyze in depth the actions taken to study the different types of telephony fraud.

Index Terms—Honeypots, VoIP, Cybercrime, Telephony fraud

I. INTRODUCTION

The invention of the telephone is one of the most important accomplishments of humankind, breaking the physical barriers of time and location and allowing two people from places miles apart to establish immediate communication. Although it was not designed to be used as an attack vector, unfortunately criminals found a way of using it as such in order to make unwanted or malicious calls to perpetrate extortion, scams and spam campaigns. These calls have been a long-standing and challenging problem, and are responsible for yearly losses of tens of millions of dollars worldwide [1], besides being very disturbing for telephone users, who feel their privacy is violated.

The recent development of Voice over IP (VoIP) has caused the telephone to be transferred to a more modern means of communication, namely the Internet, making it more accessible and cheaper for people to contact each other. These benefits have been well-received not only by ordinary users, but also by cybercriminals, who now can reduce the cost and operational complexity of these telephony campaigns, and this technology

allows them to place automated calls with little effort. These calls are typically made in the form of bot-calls, which are carried out by simple software using dialer equipment to generate vast numbers of calls to a given (or randomly chosen) list of phone numbers. Their aim is to make contact with an active recipient and trick them into performing the desired action, ultimately making them fraud victims. Generally, the instructions are transmitted via a pre-recorded message but, in some cases, they can eventually be assigned to a human agent for further interaction, although this becomes a limiting factor, since human agents may not have time to attend to all the connected calls.

In comparison with other attacks such as email spam, voice spam calls are significantly more disturbing because they require immediate attention; when the phone rings, the recipient must decide whether to accept the call and listen to it just judging by the caller ID, which is often “unknown” or even spoofed [2]. Even if the user ignores or declines the call, spammers can send a prerecorded audio message straight to the user’s voicemail, thus also having the static factor of email spam. In addition, these attacks feel more personal, since, typically, people are less inclined to give their phone number than their email address, so when an attacker is able to contact them, they gain an advantage over the recipient, who normally feels confused. Furthermore, most email spam is systematically filtered out by anti-spam algorithms, and, at the time of drafting this proposal, this type of countermeasures do not exist in telephony fraud.

Related works attempt to address the problem of malicious calls in two ways: i) statically prior to the call being established; or ii) dynamically during the call. On the one hand, several approaches have performed call request header analysis [3]. However, this type of measures are easily evaded (e.g., by using a spoofed caller ID [2]). On the other hand, recent works have leveraged automated approaches to interactively deal with unsolicited calls. Works such as [1] propose machine learning as a means to prevent malicious calls tailored to the users using features that model the normal behavior expected (e.g., weekday and time). The authors in [4] study the effectiveness of an interactive voice response system called Lenny. One of the key lessons in this work is that chatbots can be used for *scambaiting*¹ fraudsters. Finally, other authors have carried out systematic studies to understand technical support scams, uncovering the call centers underpinning this fraud using Web crawlers to find scammers, domains and phones on the Internet [5].

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¹The act of wasting the time and resources of scammers.

While recent studies have shed light on how certain parts of this ecosystem work, it is still unclear how attacks on VoIP systems contribute to this type of fraud. In this paper, we show how fraudsters leverage VoIP systems to build their infrastructure, and we provide an overview of the current status of VoIP systems and the risks arising when the system itself, or the credentials of its users, is compromised. Some of our findings include:

- Attackers use our system to carry out different types of telephony fraud as well as actions that allow them to obtain greater benefits. In particular, we identify both Toll Evasion and Revenue Share as being two of the most prevalent types of fraud. We also report a large number of cases in which attempts are made to call personal numbers (both landlines and mobile), which suggests that attacks on VoIP systems are frequently used for fraudulent purposes such as scams or spam like those described in [6]. Our work is the first to provide a quantitative study of how fraudsters use compromised VoIP systems for *fun and profit*.
- We uncover the tricks fraudsters use to evade restrictions. For instance, there are attempts to call numbers using different prefixes to avoid dial-plan restrictions. By causing an error in the parsing of these numbers, calls to restricted destinations are permitted. Calls to wrong numbers are also used to check fingerprint honeypots, e.g., when an invalid number gives them a ringtone. Learning from these tricks lets us propose countermeasures against VoIP attacks.
- We find that while a few attacks are random, many others are aware of the context surrounding the target of the attack, namely the *callee*. In particular: 1) fraudsters are aware of the mechanisms used by reputation systems to block connections from TOR nodes or known VPNs, consequently 50% of IP addresses come from compromised servers that belong to hosting companies; and 2) fraudsters try to maximize the success of their attacks by calling during office hours or hours when there usually are people at home.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II provides the system overview, the experiments carried out and the ethical considerations. Section III presents the data analysis from our experiments. Section IV describes the limitations and key findings of our study. Section V discusses the proposals from the community regarding malicious calls. Finally, the conclusions are presented in Section VI.

II. METHODOLOGY

To understand how VoIP services are misused, we deploy a honeypot and monitor the accesses and actions that take place through it. Figure 1 shows the methodology followed in this work. First, we describe the architecture of our system and the experimental setting. Next, we describe the vulnerable user accounts that have been added to our system so that attackers can gain access through them. Finally, we describe the analysis carried out and the ethical principles followed in this work.

Fig. 1. Methodology.

A. System overview

Our honeypot runs on top of a custom infrastructure with a number of VoIP accounts. The architecture consists of a Virtual Private Server (VPS) hosted in Germany. We fortify the server to prevent unauthorized access to services that are not relevant to our study. We build an Asterisk-based Private Branch Exchange (PBX) [7], which is a popular open-source communications framework. We configure our server to allow any type of call from a properly authenticated user and we redirect the calls to an enabled private extension to simulate that the call is being carried out correctly. All the accounts are subscribed to a specific dial plan that limits outgoing calls to a predefined set of countries and we restrict calls to premium numbers. The reason to restrict calls to some specific places is to simulate the legitimate behavior of a configured PBX via which it is only possible to call certain destinations.

We populate our VoIP system with a number of user names and passwords, as described in Section II-B. Each of the accounts deployed belongs to a specific context on the server and is linked to one of the dial plans that have been set up. Thus, accounts linked to a dial plan in the US, for instance, can only make calls to the US. As a result, all the calls that match the established dial plan are redirected to one of our extensions to make fraudsters believe that the calls were successful. Our system then collects logs from Asterisk in order to perform a data analysis as described in Section II-C.

B. Accounts

We design two experiments that aim to differentiate how attackers gain access to our honeypot accounts.

Weak user credentials. We set up a set of 30 user accounts with weak passwords. The user accounts are numerical identifiers designed to reproduce a setting similar to the one used in large companies or universities. Thus, each user (phone) is identified as if it were a phone extension, and this same extension number has been used as the password. We use only numerical user IDs and weak passwords in order to promptly capture automated bots running brute force attacks against VoIP services.

Strong user passwords. Our second experiment sets user accounts by using: i) numerical users, similar to how they

were created in the previous sections but this time using randomly generated strong passwords; and ii) common users created with the concatenation of a name and surname. For the generation of random names and surnames we used Enron's public email dataset [8]. This dataset was made public when the investigation into the Enron company ended. We extracted all the names and surnames, and randomly generated dummy identities which we used to create users in our VoIP system. For this latter set of users, we generated the passwords by concatenating a long list of different dictionary words to simulate passwords created by the user that can be remembered.

Account leak. The next phase of this experiment is to leak the credentials in a controlled experiment in which we record the user name and the source of the leak. We chose a series of paste sites and underground forums to leak credentials since these sites are often used to publish credentials stolen from different Internet services. We leaked 70 accounts to different chosen places, with 30 of them being published on paste sites such as pastebin.com, paste.ee and pastebin.xyz. Another 20 accounts were published in underground forums such as offensivesecurity.net and blackhatworld.com. The remaining 20 accounts were leaked in prominent Russian underground forums.

C. Data analysis

In this phase, we perform a data-driven analysis on the actions carried out in our system by the attackers and on the metadata that can be extracted from the systems that have interacted with our honeypot. In particular, our analysis first studies characterizing features from the IP addresses we receive connections from. We then reverse the password used by the attackers when attacking the authentication mechanism of the VoIP server. Finally, we analyze both the phone numbers and the metadata inferred from the call attempt. We describe all this in greater detail below.

IP address analysis. We analyze all the metadata associated with the IP addresses that interact with our system as well as the open ports of the systems associated with them. We analyze the location of these addresses to discover the origin of the attack and we also check whether these addresses appear in lists of known proxies or bots. Finally, we consult the Autonomous System Name to which the IP addresses belong as well as the open ports and vulnerabilities presented by the systems that are running behind them. It should be noted that no type of active scanning has been carried out on these IP addresses and that open-source tools available through the Internet have been consulted (e.g., VirusTotal [9], Shodan [10] and IP Intelligence [11]).

Passwords. Although in the first version of the SIP protocol the passwords travel in plain text through the network, in version 2 the SIP protocol uses a mechanism based on challenge/response to carry out user authentication [12]. Figure 2 shows the exchange of messages when a user fails to authenticate through the INVITE method. Unlike the REGISTER method, which registers the device and tells the server where it should direct the calls destined for that user, the INVITE method allows calls to be made without registering the device on the server.

Fig. 2. Authentication message flow in the SIP protocol.

Basically, the client sends an INVITE request to the server, which returns a message saying that it is not authorized, and in which it transmits a nonce and the realm to authenticate. The client computes the response using Algorithm 1 and sends it back to the server. Finally, the server computes the response and, if it matches the one sent by the user, it will send a correct authentication message, or in this case it will send a message that the authentication has not been carried out successfully.

$$\begin{aligned}
 A &= MD5(\text{user} : \text{realm} : \text{password}) \\
 B &= MD5(\text{method} : \text{sip} : \text{uri}) \\
 \text{hash} &= MD5(A : \text{nonce} : B)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Therefore, the server never sees the plain text password used by the client, which in this case is the password used by the attackers to try to identify themselves to our server. The authentication message flow of the REGISTER method is the same, with only the method parameter changing when computing the response. By using all the data collected from the authentication messages, we obtain all the variables in Algorithm 1 except the password since it is not transmitted in plain text over the network. Therefore, we use a dictionary of the most common passwords to apply brute force and find the most frequently-used passwords on our system.

Phone numbers. We analyze all the phone numbers that the attackers have tried to call through our system. We parse these numbers to extract information about whether the number is valid based on the patterns that phone numbers follow around the world. We also extract the location of the phone number based on the country code and the area code, as well as the type of phone number (e.g., land-line or mobile).

Call analysis and phone fraud. We analyze the calls that are made through our system by looking at the timestamp

of the calls that are attempted in order to check whether the calls are made while taking into account the local time of the destination or whether they are automated calls that do not use this information. Therefore, on the basis of the type of call, we classify it according to the type of fraud that is being attempted through our system and the benefits that attackers could obtain through this type of fraud.

D. Ethics

We have followed the ethical principles for Internet-mediated research in [13], which in turn, stem from The Belmont Report [14] and the Menlo Report [15]. We address the challenge of obtaining informed consent from unknown Internet users through the *beneficence* principle and by making a risk-benefit assessment. On the one hand, we have implemented strict mechanisms to minimize risks, reducing the harm to mere *annoyance*. On the other hand, our honeypot effectively reduces the surface of the attack and prevents criminals from benefiting while depleting the resources of the attackers. We also gain an understanding of the underlying ecosystem that can allow the community to further tackle telephony scams. Finally, by granting attackers access to our VoIP we deter them from using other compromised VoIP systems. Our risk-benefit assessment has been evaluated by our Institutional Review Board (IRB), who consider our decision-making ethical and have approved this study. We next detail the measures we adopted to minimize risks to privacy.

First, we limited the usage of our VoIP system by redirecting calls to a private extension, thus preventing these calls from being forwarded to their actual recipient. Second, we restricted the scope of our experiment by limiting the number of target countries. Although no external calls are made from our system, we simulate that these are being made by calling a private extension created for this purpose, so attackers may believe that these numbers exist and try to call from other systems. Finally, for the analysis of the metadata of all the attackers of the system, no active scan was performed. Instead, third-party services (e.g., Shodan [10]) were used to obtain information and geolocations.

III. DATA ANALYSIS

We ran the experiment for a period of around 4 months for accounts with weak credentials. After those 4 months, we blocked access to those weak accounts and created new accounts with strong passwords, as described in Section II-B. This experiment lasted around 2 months. During the course of both experiments, we monitored the actions performed on the VoIP server, collecting information for further analysis.

A. Overview

We deployed an Asterisk-based PBX server for our experiment. During the first period of the experiment, the server used accounts with weak credentials, while in the second part of the experiment the server used accounts with strong credentials. After parsing the information collected on our system, we detected 2,209 unique IP addresses on the server. For the first

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF THE ACTIONS PERFORMED ON THE VOIP SERVER.

Type	Calls	
	Weak Credentials	Strong Credentials
Call attempts	306,044	713
Unique phone numbers	211,113	319
Valid phone numbers	10,731	141
Possible phone numbers	34,913	98

Fig. 3. Cumulative number of calls attempts (weak and strong credentials).

period, all the accounts that were created in the VoIP system were accessed. On the other hand, out of the 70 accounts we leaked, 20 were accessed, with 12 of these having been leaked in underground forums and 8 on paste sites.

We logged the actions performed with all the accounts, which can be summarized in Table I. We see that the total number of call attempts is around 300K. Unique phone numbers amount to about 200K and represent the total of different phones to which calls were attempted. Valid and possible phone numbers are around 10K and 30K, respectively, and represent how many of these numbers are valid or may be valid on the basis of phonenumbers library [16]. Those numbers that contain the country code, the area code and the correct number length for that country are considered valid by the library. Those numbers that do not contain the country code and are considered valid are those that by size and format can match local numbers in at least one country (some of them may be valid for several regions, so it is not possible to know exactly the country to which they belong). It is important to note that the library indicates whether the number is valid based on the dialing plan of that country, but it does not mean that this number is currently owned by any user. By observing the results, it can be seen that the number of call attempts is much higher during the time that the weak credentials experiment lasted. These calls are usually generated by bots that are scanning the Internet for active VoIP servers and are looking for valid credentials by brute force and, once they find them, they start generating calls. On the other hand, when using strong credentials, with these types of attacks they cannot gain access, and the attackers who access obtained the passwords through forums or paste sites. Therefore, the number of accesses was lower, and there may even have been curious accesses made by attackers that were curious to test whether they could call for free.

Regarding the call attempts, we analyzed their timestamps for each day of the experiment. Figure 3 shows the results of this analysis. It can be easily seen that, during the experiment

with weak credentials, the number of calls increased daily while remaining constant at the end of the experiment, which is when strong passwords were used. In addition, the first calls with weak credentials occurred within a few hours of putting the server online, while with strong credentials, the first calls occurred around 20 days after leaking the credentials of the user accounts.

B. IP address analysis

In this section, we analyze the IP addresses that interacted with our system. In total, 1,280 and 1,188 unique IP addresses interacted with the server with weak and strong credentials, respectively. Between the two sets of IP addresses, 259 match on the two servers. Out of all those IP addresses, only 244 and 19 successfully logged in. The number of IP addresses that interacted with both servers is very similar in terms of the number of different addresses detected. However, it is important to note that the strong credentials experiment started immediately after the weak credentials one finished, and only 259 IP addresses coincide between the two experiments, which seems to indicate that, either the actors that are actively searching for online servers use new mechanisms to hide, or those compromised servers have detected the intrusion and have closed their access.

Location. We depict the source of the IP address in Figure 4. Blue points represent the origin of the IP addresses that interacted in the experiment with weak credentials, green represents the origin of the IP addresses that interacted in the experiment with strong credentials and red represents those IP addresses that matched in the two experiments. Germany is the most common location with 21.9% of the IP addresses collected, followed by the Netherlands (20.8%), the United States (14.9%), France (12.1%) and the Palestinian Territory (10.2%). Note that more than 50% of the IP addresses collected belong to Europe, which may indicate that the attackers are using compromised servers to perform their actions or that they connect through proxies. We also investigated the origin and destination of the calls that were attempted through our system. We only consider those calls made to valid numbers and from which the geographical location of the telephone number was extracted. Table II shows the top 20 sources and destinations of calls that were attempted with both weak and strong credentials. It can be seen that in the experiment with weak credentials most of the calls were attempted from the Netherlands, while with strong credentials they came from Palestine and the Philippines. It should be noted that this source may not be the actual location of the different actors, but may be hidden behind some proxy, Virtual Private Network (VPN) or similar system with the IP address of those countries.

Hostings. We also analyze the IP addresses through public services (e.g., VirusTotal) to search for information and see whether there are relationships between them. Although some IP addresses were previously associated with certain malware samples and domains, there does not seem to be a clear relationship between them. However, on the basis of information about the organization or ISP to which they belong, they do indicate that certain IP addresses are related

TABLE II
TOP 20 SOURCES AND DESTINATIONS OF CALLS WITH WEAK AND STRONG CREDENTIALS. THE TABLE REPRESENTS ONLY THOSE CALLS IN WHICH IT HAS BEEN POSSIBLE TO EXTRACT THE PHONE NUMBER'S GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION.

Weak Credentials			Strong Credentials		
Source	Destination	Calls	Source	Destination	Calls
DE	UK	822	PS	US	78
US	UK	742	PH	CU	33
NL	UK	488	PH	PH	25
NL	FR	407	PH	UK	11
NL	RU	387	PS	ES	8
NL	US	355	PS	IL	6
NL	BO	313	PH	BJ	5
NL	BQ	294	PS	UK	9
US	SG	273	US	US	3
NL	AW	273	US	UK	3
NL	LK	270	US	EG	3
NL	IQ	255	PH	US	3
NL	CW	213	PH	TN	3
NL	AM	207	PH	SI	3
NL	GT	191	PS	JE	3
DE	ZM	176	PS	CH	3
DE	RS	172	PS	FR	3
US	JP	171	PS	AT	3
NL	PE	171	DE	FR	3
NL	JP	171	CH	RU	2

to each other. By consulting the public databases of IP address information services, we found that 882 addresses belong to hosting services. We also consulted the remaining IP addresses via an intelligence service [11], which uses probabilistic techniques and machine learning models to determine whether an IP address is a proxy, a VPN, a hosting service, etc. Given an IP, the system returns a value between 0 and 1 that indicates how likely it is to be a "bad IP". According to the results obtained, 119 have a value greater than 0.98 indicating that these IP addresses have a high probability of being proxies or hostings. Therefore, around 45% of the IP addresses that appear in our system belong to hosting services. We plot a graph with the different IP addresses that belong to hosting services together with their autonomous system (AS). Figure 5 shows the connections between the different IP addresses collected. It can be seen that large groups of IP addresses belong to the same organization (e.g., Online S.A.S or OVH), which seems to indicate that these sites could be compromised and used by fraudsters to hide their identity. It is important to note that most of the hosting services provide servers to users and they are the ones who must take care of their management and security. Therefore, if users do not perform the necessary security updates and good maintenance of their servers, they will not be able to contain security breaches that allow attackers to take control of the system.

Open ports. We analyze the open ports of the IPs that appear in the logs of the VoIP system. Table III shows the most common open ports among the IP addresses collected. We observe that there are open ports of common services, such as HTTP, SSH, SSL, SMB, FTP or RDP. Also, one of the methods used by attackers to compromise systems is through any of these services, either because of some vulnerability or through the use of weak passwords to access through SSH. In fact, most botnets in the IoT ecosystem infect different

Fig. 4. Geographical map of the location of the IPs that interacted with our system.

TABLE III
TOP 30 MOST COMMON OPEN PORTS

IP Addresses	Port	IP Addresses	Port	IP Addresses	Port
404	80	65	445	46	995
301	443	60	8089	45	465
289	22	58	5985	44	500
163	5060	56	143	44	137
116	3389	55	993	32	8000
92	53	49	1723	32	2000
89	21	49	110	29	5222
85	123	48	111	27	8443
75	25	47	8080	27	2087
73	3306	47	587	27	2082

devices through the use of weak passwords in services such as SSH or Telnet [17] [18]. Another curious circumstance that we find regarding open ports is the appearance of ports 5060 and 3389. The former is a port belonging to UDP and which is the default port used by VoIP systems. This seems to indicate that they are tracking other VoIP systems and searching for (or using) passwords from other VoIP systems to use them on their system and make calls through other users. The latter is the port used by the RDP protocol, which is used for the remote Windows desktop. The RDP protocol contains a recent vulnerability known as BlueKeep [19], whose exploit was made public in the summer of 2019 [20]. This vulnerability allows the execution of remote code and could be used by attackers to compromise systems and use them for their interests, such as attacking the user credentials of a VoIP system or as a proxy to carry out their attacks and not reveal their real IP address.

Vulnerabilities. We consult the IP addresses through Shodan [10] in order to obtain the vulnerabilities detected in the services that are exposed to the Internet. Of all the information collected, we found 495 different Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVEs). Figure 6(a) shows the distribution by year of the vulnerabilities that have been collected through Shodan. It can be seen that there are vulnerabilities that were discovered more than 10 years ago, so it seems to indicate that not enough attention has been paid to these servers by their administrators. Also, it can be seen that they are mostly recent vulnerabilities, and that the maximum peak is reached in the vulnerabilities of 2016. It is important to note that Shodan shows the current vulnerabilities based on the software version that is running, but does not check whether the vulnerability actually exists. We obtain information on each of the CVEs in the public database of cvedetails [21]. Each CVE has an associated score that indicates the criticality of the vulnerability and its impact. Figure 6(b) shows the distribution of CVEs based on the score collected for each one in cvedetails. It can be seen that most of the CVEs have a score between 4 and 8, which corresponds to medium (4-6.9) and high (7-8.99) vulnerabilities. We can also observe that there are several CVEs with a high criticality index (9-10). Among the critical vulnerabilities that exist, most of them are related to the Hypertext Pre-Processor (PHP) interpreter. In addition, vulnerabilities appear in Windows systems with the Remote Desktop Protocol (RDP) and the Server Message Block (SMB), which are widely known for the impact they have had throughout the world [22], [23].

TABLE IV
TOP 30 MOST COMMON PASSWORDS USED IN OUR SYSTEM.

Rank	Passwords	Hits	Rank	Passwords	Hits	Rank	Passwords	Hits
1	1234	7,944	11	abcd1234	5,330	21	asdfg	2,330
2	123456	7,006	12	123abc	4,911	22	1111	2,050
3	1000	6,481	13	12345	3,501	23	8888	2,023
4	password	6,103	14	test123	2,921	24	9999	2,022
5	pass123	6,032	15	qwe123	2,540	25	1q2w3e	2,018
6	12345678	5,563	16	asd123	2,531	26	1234567	2,016
7	123123	5,545	17	test	2,491	27	111111	2,000
8	abc123	5,541	18	password123	2,466	28	123321	1,995
9	0000	5,442	19	admin123	2,423	29	123qwe	1,972
10	4321	5,431	20	secret	2,369	30	123456789	1,971

(a) CVEs distributed by the year of their appearance.

(b) CVEs distributed by their criticality score.

Fig. 6. CVEs collected from the different IPs that interacted with our honeypot.

the unique phone numbers belong mainly to Europe, Africa, Russia and the Havana and Cuba area. However, the most called frequently countries are the United Kingdom, the United States, Russia and France with 3,028, 1,063, 435 and 428 calls, respectively.

Types of phones. The type of phone numbers which the attackers tried to call has been extracted. Table V shows the different phone numbers found that were either valid or possible. It can be seen that most of them belong to mobiles or

TABLE V
TYPES OF PHONE NUMBERS THAT ATTACKERS TRIED TO CALL.

Type of phone numbers	Valid phones	Possible phones
Mobile	7,517	26,649
Fixed line	1,901	1,616
Premium rate	514	225
Fixed line or mobile	357	1,393
Universal Access Number (UAN)	180	138
Personal number	131	21
VoIP	125	317
Shared cost	62	158
Pager	55	55
Toll free	30	1,418
Voicemail	0	21

landlines. It is important to note that the possible numbers are local ones that could be valid in some region and, therefore, are not completely accurate since some regions have similar dialing plans. The fixed or mobile line row represents those telephone numbers for which it cannot be known whether they are fixed or mobile since in some regions it is impossible to distinguish between a fixed or mobile number by looking at the telephone number (e.g., the USA). The rest of the phone numbers are as follows:

- Premium rate. Telephone numbers through which different services are offered and whose call prices are higher than a conventional call.
- UAN. This is a phone number that allows a company to have several lines associated with it. In this way, when the UAN number is called, one of these lines will be reached depending on, for example, the geographical location or the time of the call.
- Personal number. This corresponds to virtual phone numbers belonging to the United Kingdom. These phone numbers allow the routing of phone call to another number and have been reported as being used for fraudulent purposes such as fraud or spam [25].
- VoIP. Phone numbers that are assigned to a user instead of a specific phone line. These are contracted through VoIP service providers.
- Shared cost. Telephone numbers for which the cost of the call is divided between the owner of the number and the one who makes the call.
- Pager. Phone numbers assigned to devices that are capable of receiving and displaying messages, also known as “beepers” [26].
- Toll free. These are free phone numbers for the person

Fig. 7. Geographical map of the location of the phones.

making the call, as the cost is billed to the owner of the phone number.

The rest of the telephone numbers that attackers attempted to call are invalid, that is, the size or dial plan does not match any region. However, most of these numbers do consist of valid numbers that have been concatenated with numbers or symbols at the beginning. For example, the telephone number `*0000000000*4412XXXXXXX` is not valid, but it can be seen that, if the initial part is omitted, the number that remains is a valid number² with country code 44, which is the code for the United Kingdom. This is repeated for all the invalid numbers with different digits, symbols and size. We believe it may be a way to try to evade the established dial plan or to know whether they are in a honeypot. For example, if calls to numbers that are not valid give a ringtone, it may indicate that the system is a honeypot.

Types of fraud. As we mentioned above, we rely on the taxonomy described in [6] to identify the different fraud schemes that were attempted through our system. This taxonomy identifies the different weaknesses and techniques that lead to the different types of fraud and the benefits that they can generate. First, we look at the different fraud schemes identified and the possible benefits attackers can obtain through them. Then, we examine the weaknesses and techniques that allow fraudsters to carry out such actions. The fraud schemes detected are the following:

- **Toll Evasion Fraud.** This type of fraud is the best known and most widely used over recent years in telephone networks. It is based on making calls without having to pay the charges of the call, which are billed to another party. In this specific case, when accessing the user accounts of a PBX to call, it is the owner of the PBX or the user of the compromised account that is charged for the calls. The benefits can range from simply not paying for anonymous calls involving criminal activities to committing other types of fraud.
- **Revenue Share Fraud.** This type of fraud occurs when an agreement is made between an operator (or a third-party service provider) and a fraudster in which the latter is responsible of making telephone calls to certain numbers owned by the former (e.g., international premium rate service numbers), generating a revenue which is then shared between them. The benefit of this type of fraud is purely economic, and the more call traffic that is generated, the greater the benefit will be for the fraudsters.
- **Voice Spam and Scams.** This scheme includes any type of unwanted or abusive calls, such as spam calls or scams. These calls can be made in many ways, from a phishing call posing as a company to telemarketing to robocalling with prerecorded messages. The possible benefits that can be obtained through this type of fraud include collecting information about the users (e.g., whether the phone belongs to a real user), and convincing or deceiving the recipients of the call to carry out some action that could also have some economic benefit for the fraudster.

²We have replaced part of the original number with the letter X so that it cannot be recognized.

The techniques and weaknesses on which these types of attacks are based within the VoIP system are similar. Basically, part of the problem of fraud over mobile phone lines comes from the interconnection of multiple technologies and the existence of a large number of operators and services. There is a lot of variation in the regulation and laws concerning telephony between different countries, which has contributed to an increase over recent years in the amount of telephone fraud. In our experiment, attackers gained access through accounts with weak passwords and account leaks on different paste and forum sites. Although this was done on purpose in order to know what happens when fraudsters have access to a system, it often happens that users with little security awareness use weak passwords and unwittingly allow third parties to access their systems. The techniques available for VoIP aim to compromise a PBX server or user accounts to make calls, even simultaneous ones, in order to increase a fraudster's benefits. Fraud schemes can be related to each other since, in this case, all schemes start with avoiding the cost of the calls that are made. It is important to note that no type of fraud was committed through our honeypot since the calls were directed to an internal extension and were not routed to the telephone network.

E. Timestamp analysis

In this section, we provide a timestamp analysis focused on calls to the United Kingdom and the United States, which are the two countries that were called the most (based on the numbers obtained as valid and for which it was possible to obtain data on their geographical location). We use local time for both countries on the basis of the time zone to which the phone number belongs. Figure 8 shows the graph of calls to each country, distributed both by the times at which the call occurred and the day of the week, regardless of whether they were made in the experiment for weak or strong credentials. By looking at the graphs, we can observe that the time of the calls is targeted at the local customs, that is, they are mainly made during office hours and between 8:00 and midnight, when it is common for people to be at home. Also, it can be seen that, for the UK, a percentage of calls are made between 00.00 and 03.59, which could indicate that certain types of bots make calls once they access the system regardless of the time or day. Regarding the day of the week, we observe that calls are made on any day and that in the UK the number of calls spikes on Thursday, Friday and Saturday. By contrast, in the United States, the number of calls per day is similar, reaching its peak midweek.

IV. DISCUSSION

In this section we discuss the limitations of our work, as well as the findings of the study.

A. Limitations

We encountered a number of limitations in the course of the experiments. On the one hand, due to the ethical requirements that this type of experiments have, calls were not routed to the

(a) Number of calls made per day of the week.

(b) Number of calls made by time slot.

Fig. 8. Number of calls that were made to the United States and the United Kingdom. The time zone used is the local time of the geographic location of the phone numbers.

telephone network; instead, those calls that coincided with the dial plan were directed to a private extension to simulate that calls were routed correctly. Some attackers may be trying to call a phone number they have control over to check whether the calls are being made correctly. This can cause some of the attackers to realize that they are in a system with certain limitations and thus not to carry out any of the actions that they would perform in a real system. On the other hand, when we carried out credential leaks, these were made on public paste sites and in underground public forums that allow the free registration of any user. For example, in private forums, users rely more on the information provided by other users since an invitation is needed to be part of that community.

B. Key-findings

In this work we have shown that VoIP attacks are a threat that underpins part of the malicious call ecosystem. We next summarize the key findings of our work.

Depleting. We noted that scammers tried to call certain phone numbers several times. This seems to indicate that they obtain phone numbers through leaked or purchased databases [3] and attempt to call them once they have access to a system. Related works have shown that depleting is effective against spam [27]. Using a honeypot may help organizations to keep a list of the phone numbers that scammers call and thus minimize the number of spam calls, which can be very annoying (e.g., when there are call attempts to a number whose caller is trying to make other calls at the same time).

Source attacks. Although we know that attackers may use other services to hide their identity, most logged IP addresses come from Europe. As we saw in Section III-B, many of them are related and belong to the same organization. Most of these organizations provide hosting services or private and virtual servers for users to set up their own services. Everything seems to indicate that the attackers exploit known vulnerabilities in services hosted on these machines as the software has often not been properly patched. Although nowadays many resources and efforts are invested in raising awareness among users regarding security issues and keeping their systems up to date, there are still many vulnerable devices accessible from the Internet that have not received the necessary patches.

Calls. We observed that most of the calls that are directed to the United States and the United Kingdom are made within the time zone corresponding to each country, thus increasing the chances of their success. Although it is true that some calls fall outside the usual time slot, indicating that the bots in question make calls without checking to which country the call is directed. In addition, call patterns have been found to generate numbers that are invalid. As we saw in Section III-D, these numbers are made up of valid numbers to which prefixes of different sizes have been added with numbers or symbols. This indicates that the bots are trying to actively bypass the restrictions of the dial plan used by the VoIP server. Introducing prefixes can cause errors in the mechanism used to enforce restrictions, which in turn can let attackers evade these mechanisms and make calls. This behavior, however, is very noisy and can be leveraged to design a system to systematically detect these bots.

Accounts. Fraudsters actively search for user accounts, scanning the Internet for known VoIP server ports to which they try to connect and apply brute-force login credentials. In addition, they also make use of leaked accounts on different sites, and it is more than likely that sales of stolen accounts will even take place. Although with strong credentials far fewer calls were made compared with accounts with weak credentials, attackers did access the former and similar behaviors were observed.

C. Countermeasures

In this section we describe a series of countermeasures to fortify VoIP servers and thus prevent a fraudulent use being made of them.

Accounts. As we have seen, attackers scan VoIP servers and make connection attempts by sweeping users and passwords in order to find weak credentials that allow them to gain access. Depending on the server configuration, it is possible to enumerate valid users based on the response from the server. In the authentication process, the server can respond with the message "Not Found" or "Unauthorized" [28] depending on whether the user is correct or not. A good practice is to configure the server so that the response is the same regardless of whether the user exists but the password is incorrect or the user does not exist. Also, on the basis of the brute force attacks received, we can see that most of them attack numeric users, so using named users would make the task of finding users more difficult for the attackers. Finally, in the event of an

attacker obtaining valid credentials, either by brute force or by theft, for example by using malware on mobile devices, a good measure is to continuously monitor the calls made and limit the number of simultaneous calls that can be made through the server. Usually, once they access the server, the attackers try to make numerous simultaneous calls, which can cause great economic losses [29].

Dial plan. Fraudsters try to make calls to phone numbers in different parts of the world including attempts to call strange phone numbers in order to avoid the restrictions of the dial plan configured for the user. It is important to implement a correct dial plan configuration and only allow calls to places where you operate or where you usually make calls, including implicit rules for the types of number you want to allow and disable calls to international and premium numbers.

Architecture. To deal with attacks against SIP servers, a good measure is to implement an SIP proxy server (e.g., Kamailio [30]). This allows you to load balance and redirect valid packets to the corresponding SIP server and release the load from the SIP server. Through a proxy, security is increased since it makes it possible to discard and ban brute-force attacks, ban the default user agent of known tools (e.g., Sipvicious [31] or Sipsan [32]), and implement other security measures. It is also possible to ban brute-force attempts on the server itself via iptables with solutions such as Fail2ban [33]. Another good measure is to change the default port of the SIP server to avoid being found by automatic scanners looking for the default VoIP ports.

V. RELATED WORK

In this section we compare this paper with previous related works.

Honeygot systems. Nawrocki et al. [34] review the state of the art of the different honeygot software systems and the data they collect by making a classification based on the type of interaction that the attackers have as well as the services and applications they emulate. Luo et al. [35] propose a honeygot system for different Internet of Things (IoT) architectures with the aim of detecting attacks or even zero days at their earliest stage. Similar work is carried out in [36], in which support is provided for eight IoT architectures and connections based on the Telnet protocol. Unlike previous works, Dowling et al. [37] propose a method for Wireless Personal Area Networks (WPAN) which enables the detection of different types of attack in the Zigbee protocol, which is part of WPAN. These types of honeygot mainly are mainly focused on detecting attacks that occur on their systems in order to detect new threats or types of attack aimed at compromising a system or violating the privacy of users. Our approach is a real VoIP system, configured to limit attackers and focused on obtaining knowledge through the attacks and actions carried out through it.

Honeygot accounts. Kaur et al. [38] carry out a review of all the related works on the different approaches designed to combat spam and compromised accounts in social networks by analyzing each of the previous studies and discussing their pros and cons. Bursztein et al. [39] study the manual hijacking

of accounts with a focus on emails and phishing websites intended for Google users. The study focuses on how user credentials are captured by attackers and used once they access the user's account. Onaolapo et al. [40] carry out a similar investigation with the difference that, instead of focusing on phishing attacks, they use a broader threat model by looking at user credentials in Gmail that have been automatically stolen by malware. They also analyze the behavior of cybercriminals when they gain access through leaked credentials on paste sites and forums. Other studies have focused on the study of user accounts that were under the control of spammers in different social networks. Thomas et al. [41] investigate the abuse by spammers of the social network Twitter. To do this, they collect a dataset of all tweets from the accounts that were suspended by the tweeter to characterize the behavior of spammers in the social network. Stringhini et al. [42] analyze the behavior of spammers in social networks using 300 honey accounts in three of the main social networks in order to develop techniques that allow detecting spammers. Unlike our work, they focus on identifying the behavior of user accounts belonging to social networks and email instead of the behavior of attackers in compromised VoIP accounts. In our study, we use "real" accounts that are obtained by attackers through brute force attacks and in different forums or paste sites trying to mimic that they have been stolen accounts.

Telephone spam and scams. Tu et al. [3] carried a review of the state of the art of the techniques used against telephone scams. They describe the ecosystem of spam calls focusing on the differences with spam in emails. Finally, they analyze the different existing solutions against telephone spam. Miramirkhani et al. [5] propose the first study of the technical support of the scams and the call centers that are behind them. They build an automatic system to detect phone numbers and domains that are used by scammers. Finally, they make calls to the numbers of the scammers to interact with them and collect statistical details of the techniques and the process used by them. Li et al. [1] design a set of features to feed machine learning algorithms in order to detect spam calls and scams. As they have no access to mobile telephony infrastructures, they develop a mobile application for users to label calls as malicious and thus enable them to build a dataset to analyze and extract features. Sahin et al. [4] use a chatbot to connect unwanted calls to the bot, which mimics a person's behavior. Although the chatbot used is not based on any advanced artificial intelligence, it proves very effective, managing to keep calls for 10 minutes, causing spammers to waste time and resources interacting with a bot. Tu et al. [2] conduct a study to understand why users fall into traps and end up being victims of scams. To do this, they conduct 10 telephone phishing experiments on 3,000 university students. Among all the possible factors that could exist to carry out the deception successfully, they observe that the impersonation of the caller's ID prevailed in most cases. Bullée et al. [43] conduct a study on the awareness of workers regarding the social engineering attacks they may receive, in this case over the telephone. According to the results obtained, they verify that scam awareness campaigns reduce user exposure only for a short period of time. In general, previous work is focused

on detecting scam calls when they are received and interacting with scammers either by directly calling the phone numbers recorded via the Internet or with a chatbot when receiving calls. On the contrary, our work is focused on how scammers obtain infrastructure or resources to make calls at no cost and what type of actions they perform by monitoring a real VoIP system, thus providing insights into what types of fraud are currently being carried out through compromised VoIP systems..

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Telephony fraud has been a long-standing and challenging problem since the invention of the telephone. Unfortunately, with the emergence of VoIP, fraudsters now have access to a more powerful technology which allows them to carry out more sophisticated and complex attacks, and to target an immense number of victims.

In this paper, we have presented a study of the behavior of criminals when they acquire VoIP user accounts, either through the use of brute force or by using accounts leaked via paste sites or through underground markets. In order to do so, we built a VoIP honeypot and established two experiments: one using accounts with weak credentials, and the other with strong credentials that were previously leaked. Then, we studied how scammers used these compromised accounts and provided a holistic overview of their activity, including provenance and intent. The different types of fraud that were attempted through our systems were identified, as well as the techniques used to increase the possible benefit that the fraudsters can obtain through these attacks.

The results show that more than 50% of the fraudsters that interacted with the system did so through IP addresses in Europe, with the Netherlands making the highest number of outgoing calls. The UK was the most called country on the basis of the valid phone numbers that were dialed, followed by the USA. Furthermore, it was noted that a large number of the IP addresses detected belonged to hosting services, which seems to indicate that these sites were compromised by fraudsters and used to hide their identity. This assumption is also supported by the fact that, after analyzing these IP addresses, we found that they had multiple commonly opened ports, as well as others that are less ordinary, such as the one used for the RDP protocol, which is known to have a high criticality vulnerability. In fact, the addresses were scanned for vulnerabilities, obtaining results indicating that most of them were of medium and high criticality.

With this work, we have managed to gain a better understanding of the actions performed by attackers when they have access to a VoIP server, and we hope that our findings are of benefit to the research community.

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